

Effect of Substituents on the Dehydration of 4-Hydroxy-Dihydroisocoumarin

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The synthesis of isocoumarin from isochroman-1,4-dione is described.

3-Phenylisochroman-1,4-dione (I) on mild reduction with tin and hydrochloric acid gave 4-hydroxydihydroisocoumarin (II) which when heated with acetic anhydride was dehydrated to give 3-phenylisocoumarin (III)¹. Seeking to extend the generality of this reaction for the synthesis of isocoumarins having no substituent in the benzene as well as the heterocyclic rings, reduction of isochroman-1,4-dione (Ia)² have been studied in this laboratory.

Methyl hydrogen phthalate³ obtained by an improved method was converted to isochroman-1,4-dione (Ia)² which on reduction with tin and hydrochloric acid though gave the expected 4-hydroxydihydroisocoumarin (IIa), it did not cyclise to the isocoumarin (IIIa) when heated with acetic anhydride, rather an altogether different product 4-acetoxydihydroisocoumarin (IIb) was obtained which could be reconverted to IIa on deacetylation. IIa could, however, be cyclised when sublimed in vacuo with KHSO₄ to the isocoumarin (IIIa). IIa could also be transformed with thionyl chloride or phosphorus pentachloride to the hitherto unknown 4-chlorodihydroisocoumarin (IIc). This leads us to conclude that there is a definite effect of the substituent of the heterocyclic ring to the dehydration of the hydroxydihydroisocoumarin.

Reduction of isochroman-1,4-dione with sodium borohydride in methanol has however failed to furnish the desired product IIa, rather a different product m.p. 149–150° was obtained which being not the material of our choice no attempt for its identification was made.

1. Wanag and Walhe, *Ber.*, 1938, **71**, 1448; R. C. Elderfield, *Heterocyclic Compounds*, Vol. II, John Wiley and Sons, New York, (1951), p. 221-222.
2. P. M. Duggleby and G. Holt., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 3581.
3. F. J. Bistow, *Nature*, 1948, **162**, 1004.

EXPERIMENTAL

All m.p.s. are uncorrected. Light petroleum used had b.p. 60–80°.

Methylhydrogenphthalate: It was prepared by a modified procedure³. To a well stirred slurry of phthalic anhydride (20 g.) in methanol (20 ml.), KOH powder was added in instalments. During the addition, the whole solution became warm and a clear solution was obtained after addition of KOH powder (1.5–2.0 g.). The homogeneous solution was diluted with water to turbidity and acidified with conc. HCl (congo red). The oil which separated solidified on cooling in the ice-chest overnight. The solid was filtered and crystallised from light petroleum to give methylhydrogenphthalate (20.5 g.; 90%), m.p. 84–85° (lit³ m.p. 82°).

4-Hydroxydihydroisocoumarin (IIa): To isochroman-1,4-dione (1.62 g.; 0.01 mole) in ethanol (20 ml.) was added HCl (1 : 1; 10 ml.), tin powder (1.5 g.) and refluxed for 2 hr. on water bath. The reaction mixture was filtered hot, alcohol distilled off and the residual solution poured in ice water. The homogeneous solution thus obtained was extracted with ether, solvent evaporated off and the residue crystallised from ethylacetate-light petroleum to give 4-hydroxydihydroisocoumarin as colourless needles (1.3 g.; 80%), m.p. 117–118°. (Found: C, 65.2; H, 4.6. C₉H₈O₃ requires: C, 65.8; H, 4.8%).

4-Acetoxydihydroisocoumarin (IIb): A mixture of 4-hydroxydihydroisocoumarin (0.164 g.; 0.01 mole) and acetic anhydride (10 ml.) was refluxed for 4 hr. and the reaction mixture poured in crushed ice when a homogeneous solution was obtained on stirring. This was extracted with ether, solvent evaporated off to give white residue which on crystallisation from ether gave 4-acetoxydihydroisocoumarin (1.5 g.; 80%), m.p. 122–123°. (Found: C, 61.0; H, 5.2. C₁₀H₁₀O₄ requires: C, 61.3; H, 5.1%).

4-Chlorodihydroisocoumarin (IIc): A slurry of 4-hydroxydihydroisocoumarin (0.65 g.; 0.004 mole) in ether (10 ml.) was added with SOCl₂ and refluxed on steam bath for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled, poured in crushed ice and agitated when layers separated. Next day, the solid that separated was collected, triturated with water and again filtered. The residue on crystallisation from chlorobenzene gave 4-chlorodihydroisocoumarin as pale needles (0.25 g.; 40%), m.p. 198–199°. (Found: C, 56.3; H, 4.0; Cl, 21.1. C₉H₇O₂Cl requires: C, 56.5; H, 4.1; Cl, 20.8%). IR (KBr) 760 cm⁻¹ (C–Cl bond), 1715 cm⁻¹ (dihydroisocoumarin).

Isocoumarin (IIIa): A mixture of 4-hydroxydihydroisocoumarin (0.25 g.) and KHSO₄ (1 g.) was sublimed in vacuo (bath temp. 150°/3 mm.) and the sublimate after one crystallisation from ethylacetate-light petroleum afforded the isocoumarin as colourless needles (0.15 g.), m.p. 45–46° (lit⁴ m.p. 47°). IR (KBr) 1740 cm⁻¹, 1755 cm⁻¹.

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4. S. I. Heilbron and H. N. Bundury, Dictionary of Organic Compounds, Eyre and Spottiswoode (1953), p. 81.